

UYURMA-OQIM KO'RINISHIDAGI NAVYE-STOKS TENGLAMALAR SISTEMASINI SONLI YECHISH

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ANNOTATSIYA

“Uyurma-oqim” ko'rinishidagi Navye-Stoks tenglamalar sistemasini sonli modellashtirish masalasi qaralgan. Masalani sonli yechishda uyurma tenglamasi o'zgaruvchan yo'nalishli usullarga kiruvchi Pismen-Rekford sxemasi va yuqori relaksatsiyali iteratsiya usuli qo'llaniladi. Aniq yechim bilan solishtirib yuqoridagi usullarning samarali ekanligi ko'rsatildi.

KIRISH

Hozirgi vaqtda ikki o'lchamli Navye-Stoks tenglamalarini sonli yechish uchun ko'plab ishlar bag'ishlangan. Bugungi kunga kelib, “uyurma-oqim” ko'rinishidagi ikki o'lchovli Navye-Stoks tenglamalari asosida yopishqoq siqilmaydigan suyuqlik muammolarini sonli modellashtirishga bag'ishlangan ko'plab tadqiqotlar mavjud.

Shunga qaramay, yuqoridagi muammoni sonli modellashtirish uchun ma'lum usullarni qo'llash samaradorligi masalasi dolzarbdir.

[1] maqolada tabiiy o'zgaruvchilarda Navye-Stoks tenglamalarini sonli yechish usuli taklif qilinadi. Usul harakat tenglamasi va uzluksizlik tenglamasini chekli ayirmali approksimatsiyasi yordamida birgalikda yechishga asoslangan. [2] da yopishqoq siqilmaydigan suyuqlikning (fizik o'zgaruvchilarda) Navye-Stoks tenglamalarini yechishning sonli usuli berilgan. Taklif qilingan usulda, tenglamalar issiqlik o'tkazuvchanligi tenglamalari bilan to'ldirilgan. Uni qurishda dastlabki operatorlarni maxsus usulda fizik jarayonlarga bo'lish bilan taqribiy faktorizatsiya sxemasidan foydalaniladi. [3] da tuzilgan to'rlarda “tezlik-bosim” o'zgaruvchilarida to'liq Navye-Stoks tenglamalarini yechishda bosimni hisoblashning yangi yondashuvi taklif qilingan. Usul uzluksizlik tenglamasining integral shakllari va bosimning

parchalanishidan foydalanishga asoslangan bo‘lib, ular asosida yordamchi masala tuziladi.

[4] da, tezlik-bosim o‘zgaruvchilari Navye-Stoks tenglamalarining to‘liq sistemasi yopishqoq siqilmaydigan suyuqlik holati uchun sonli chekli ayirmalar usuli bilan yechiladi.

Navye-Stoks tenglamalarini “uyurma-oqim” ko‘rinishiga keltirish sonli modellashtirishni ancha osonlashtiradi. “Uyurma-oqim” ko‘rinishidagi Navye-Stoks tenglamalarini sonli modellashtirish bo‘yicha batafsil ma’lumotlarni [5, 6] da qarash mumkin.

Yuqoridagi ishlardan ayirmali o‘laroq, ushbu ishda “uyurma-oqim” Navye-Stoks tenglamalar sistemasini sonli yechish uchun o‘zgaruvchan yo‘nalishlar usullari (Pismen-Rekford sxemasidan) va yuqori relaksatsiyali iteratsiya usulini birgalikda qo‘llab sonli natijalar olingan. Bunday holda, (1) uyurma tenglamalarini sonli yechish uchun Pismen-Rekford usuli va (2) oqim funktsiyasi tenglamasini yechish uchun esa yuqori relaksatsiyali iteratsiya usuli yordamida sonli yechiladi.

1. Masalaning qo‘yilishi. Dekart koordinatalarida Navye-Stoks tenglamalari sistemasi «uyurma-oqim» ko‘rinishida quyidagicha yoziladi [7].

$$\frac{\partial \omega}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} = \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial y^2} \right) + Q(t, x, y), \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial y^2} = -\omega, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} = u, \quad \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} = -v, \quad \omega = \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}. \quad (3)$$

bu yerda x, y – fazoviy koordinatalar, t – vaqt u va v tezlik vektorining koordinata o‘qlaridagi proyeksiyasi, ν – kinematik qovushqoqlik koeffitsienti, ψ – oqim funktsiyasi, ω – uyurma funktsiyasi, Q – ma’lum funktsiya.

$\bar{D} : \{(x, y, t) \in [0,1] \times [0,1] \times [0,T]\}$ sohada (1), (2) sistema uchun biz quyidagi chegaraviy shartlarni beramiz:

$$\psi|_{x=0} = 0, \quad \psi|_{x=1} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x}|_{x=0} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x}|_{x=1} = 0, \quad 0 \leq y \leq 1, \quad (4)$$

$$\psi|_{y=0} = 0, \quad \psi|_{y=1} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y}|_{x=0} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y}|_{x=1} = 0, \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1, \quad (5)$$

$t=0$ da boshlang'ich shartlar quyidagi ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi:

$$\psi(0, x, y) = 0, \quad \omega(0, x, y) = 0. \quad (6)$$

2. Chekli-ayirmali approksimatsiya. \bar{D} sohada x, y fazoviy koordinatalarda tekis to'rni kiritamiz:

$$\bar{\Omega}_h = \left\{ x_i = ih, \quad y_j = jh, \quad 0 \leq i, j \leq N, \quad h = \frac{1}{N} \right\}$$

va t vaqt bo'yicha to'r ushbu ko'rinishda kiritiladi:

$$\bar{\Omega}_\tau = \{t_k = k\tau, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, M\}, \quad \text{bunda } \tau = T / M.$$

(1), (2) differensial tenglamalar sistemasi $\bar{\Omega} = \bar{\Omega}_h \times \bar{\Omega}_\tau$ ayirmali to'rda approksimatsiya qilinadi.

(1) uyurma tenglamasini sonli yechish uchun biz o'zgaruvchan yo'nalishlar usulini qo'llaymiz (Pisman-Rekford sxemasi) [8]. Bu sxema oshkormas absolyut turg'un sxemadir. Pismen-Rekford sxemasi approksimatsiya xatoligi $\theta(\tau^2 + |h|^2)$, bu yerda $|h|^2 = h_1^2 + h_2^2$.

(1) tenglamani Pismen-Rekford sxemasi bilan approksimatsiyalaymiz. Ushbu sxemada k qatlamdan $k + 1$ qatlamga o'tish ikki bosqichda amalga oshiriladi. Birinchi bosqichda oraliq qiymatlar $\omega_{i,j}^{k+1/2}$ quyidagi tenglamalar sistemasidan aniqlanadi

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\omega_{i,j}^{k+1/2} - \omega_{i,j}^k}{0,5\tau} + \frac{\omega_{i+1,j}^{k+1/2} - \omega_{i-1,j}^{k+1/2}}{2h} \frac{\psi_{i,j+1}^k - \psi_{i,j-1}^k}{2h} - \\ & - \frac{\omega_{i,j+1}^k - \omega_{i,j-1}^k}{2h} \frac{\psi_{i+1,j}^k - \psi_{i-1,j}^k}{2h} = \frac{\nu}{h^2} (\omega_{i+1,j}^{k+1/2} - 2\omega_{i,j}^{k+1/2} + \omega_{i-1,j}^{k+1/2}) + \\ & + \frac{\nu}{h^2} (\omega_{i,j+1}^k - 2\omega_{i,j}^k + \omega_{i,j-1}^k) + Q(t_{k+1/2}, x_i, y_i), \\ & i, j = 1, 2, \dots, N - 1 \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, M - 1, \end{aligned}$$

(7)

ikkinchi bosqichda esa topilgan $\omega_{i,j}^{k+1/2}$ qiymatlardan foydalanib, tenglamalar sistemasidagi $\omega_{i,j}^{k+1}$ qiymatlar quyidagi ayirmali tenglamalardan aniqlanadi

$$\frac{\omega_{i,j}^{k+1} - \omega_{i,j}^{k+1/2}}{0,5\tau} + \frac{\omega_{i+1,j}^{k+1/2} - \omega_{i-1,j}^{k+1/2}}{2h} \frac{\Psi_{i,j+1}^k - \Psi_{i,j-1}^k}{2h} - \frac{\omega_{i,j+1}^{k+1} - \omega_{i,j-1}^{k+1}}{2h} \frac{\Psi_{i+1,j}^k - \Psi_{i-1,j}^k}{2h} = \frac{v}{h^2} (\omega_{i+1,j}^{k+1/2} - 2\omega_{i,j}^{k+1/2} + \omega_{i-1,j}^{k+1/2}) + \frac{v}{h^2} (\omega_{i,j+1}^{k+1} - 2\omega_{i,j}^{k+1} + \omega_{i,j-1}^{k+1}) + Q(t_{k+1}, x_i, y_i),$$

$$i, j = 1, 2, \dots, N-1 \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, M-1.$$

(8)

Oqim funksiyasi uchun (2) tenglama quyidagi ayirma sxemasi bilan approksimatsiyalanadi

$$\frac{\Psi_{i+1,j}^{k+1} - 2\Psi_{i,j}^{k+1} + \Psi_{i-1,j}^{k+1}}{h^2} + \frac{\Psi_{i,j+1}^{k+1} - 2\Psi_{i,j}^{k+1} + \Psi_{i,j-1}^{k+1}}{h^2} = -\omega_{ij}^{k+1}$$

yoki

$$\frac{\Psi_{i+1,j}^{k+1} + \Psi_{i-1,j}^{k+1} + \Psi_{i,j+1}^{k+1} + \Psi_{i,j-1}^{k+1} - 4\Psi_{i,j}^{k+1}}{h^2} = -\omega_{ij}^{k+1} \quad (9)$$

$$i, j = 1, 2, \dots, N-1 \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, M-1.$$

(3) tenglama quyidagicha approksimatsiya qilinadi

$$u_{i,j}^{k+1} = \frac{\Psi_{i,j+1}^{k+1} - \Psi_{i,j-1}^{k+1}}{2h}, \quad v_{i,j}^{k+1} = -\frac{\Psi_{i+1,j}^{k+1} - \Psi_{i-1,j}^{k+1}}{2h} \quad (10)$$

$$i, j = 1, 2, \dots, N-1 \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, M-1.$$

3. Sonli yechish algoritmi. Keling, oddiy iteratsiya usulini qo'llash uchun (9) ayirmali tenglamalarni quyidagi qulay shaklda qayta yozamiz [9]

$$\Psi_{ij}^{k+1,s+1} = \Psi_{ij}^{k+1,s} + r_{ij}, \quad (11)$$

Bu yerda

$$r_{ij} = \frac{\Psi_{i+1,j}^{k+1,s} + \Psi_{i-1,j}^{k+1,s} + \Psi_{i,j+1}^{k+1,s} + \Psi_{i,j-1}^{k+1,s} - 4\Psi_{i,j}^{k+1,s} + h^2 w_{ij}^{k+1}}{4}.$$

(12)

Iteratsiya yaqinlashuvi tezligi yuqori relaksatsiyali iteratsiya usulini qo'llash bilan yaxshilanadi [10]. Ketma -ket yuqori relaksatsiyali iteratsiya usuli quyidagi iteratsiya sxemadan foydalanadi

$$\Psi_{ij}^{k+1,s+1} = \Psi_{ij}^{k+1,s} + \vartheta \left(\frac{\Psi_{i+1,j}^{k+1,s} + \Psi_{i-1,j}^{k+1,s} + \Psi_{i,j+1}^{k+1,s} + \Psi_{i,j-1}^{k+1,s} - 4\Psi_{i,j}^{k+1,s} + h^2 w_{ij}^{k+1}}{4} \right) = \Psi_{ij}^{k+1,s} + \vartheta r_{ij},$$

(13)

bu erda parametr ϑ hududga tegishli $1 \leq \vartheta < 2$. ϑ parametrni optimal tanlash chiziqli sistemalar uchun iteratsiya matritsalarining xos qiymatlariga bog'liq va ko'rib chiqilayotgan masala uchun quyidagi formula bo'yicha beriladi. [4].

$$\vartheta = \frac{4}{2 + \sqrt{4 - 4 \cos^2 \frac{\pi}{N-1}}} = \frac{4}{2 + 2\sqrt{1 - \cos^2 \frac{\pi}{N-1}}} = \frac{2}{1 + \sin \frac{\pi}{N-1}}.$$

Oqim funksiyasi uchun ayirma tenglamalarning

Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден. oddiy iteratsiya, iteratsiyalar soni bo'yicha yechimlari $n_0(\varepsilon)$ talab qilinadi. Belgilangan aniqlikka erishish uchun [5] ε aniqlikda formula bilan aniqlanadi .

$$n_0(\varepsilon) \approx \frac{2 \ln(1/\varepsilon)}{\pi^2 h^2}, \quad (14)$$

Yuqori relaksatsiya usuli uchun mos keladigan iteratsiyalar soni quyidagi shaklga ega:

$$n_0(\varepsilon) \approx \frac{2 \ln(1/\varepsilon)}{\pi h}. \quad (15)$$

$h = 0,05$, $\varepsilon = 10^{-3}$ bo'lganda (14) va (15) formulalar bo'yicha talab qilinadigan maksimal iteratsiyalar soni taxminan 560 va 88 ga teng bo'ladi. Ko'rinib turibdiki, oqim tenglamasini yechish uchun yuqori relaksatsiya usulidan foydalanish maqsadga muvofiqdir .

(7),(8) ayirmali tenglamalarni yechish algoritmini batafsil bayon etamiz.

Dastlab (7) tenglama ushbu standart shaklga keltiriladi

$$\bar{A}_i \omega_{i-1,j}^{k+1/2} - \bar{C}_i \omega_{i,j}^{k+1/2} + \bar{B}_i \omega_{i+1,j}^{k+1/2} = -\bar{F}_{i,j}^k, \quad (16)$$

$$i, j = 1, 2, \dots, N-1 \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, M-1.$$

Bu yerda

$$\bar{A}_i = 0,5\tau \left[\frac{\nu}{h^2} - \frac{1}{4h} (\psi_{i,j+1}^k - \psi_{i,j-1}^k) \right], \quad \bar{B}_i = 0,5\tau \left[\frac{\nu}{h^2} + \frac{1}{4h} (\psi_{i,j+1}^k - \psi_{i,j-1}^k) \right],$$

$$\bar{C}_i = 1 + \frac{\tau\nu}{h^2}, \quad \bar{F}_{i,j}^k = \omega_{i,j}^k + \frac{0,5\tau\nu}{h^2} (\omega_{i,j+1}^k - 2\omega_{i,j}^k + \omega_{i,j-1}^k) +$$

$$+ \frac{0,5\tau}{4h} (\omega_{i,j+1}^k - \omega_{i,j-1}^k) (\psi_{i+1,j}^k - \psi_{i-1,j}^k) + Q(t_{k+1/2}, x_i, y_i).$$

(16) ayirmali tenglama progonka usuli bilan yechiladi , buning uchun ayirmali to'ring barcha tugunlaridagi $\omega_{ij}^{k+1/2}$ qiymatlarni aniqlash uchun $O(N^2)$ arifmetik amallar kerak bo'ladi.

Barcha $\omega_{ij}^{k+1/2}$ lar topilgandan so'ng, (8) ayirmali tenglamani yechish uchun uni standart shaklga keltiramiz:

$$A_j \omega_{i,j-1}^{k+1} - C_j \omega_{i,j}^{k+1} + B_j \omega_{i,j+1}^{k+1} = -F_{i,j}^{k+1/2}, \quad (17)$$

$$i, j = 1, 2, \dots, N-1 \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, M-1.$$

Bu yerda

$$A_j = 0.5\tau \left[\frac{\nu}{h^2} - \frac{1}{4h} (\psi_{i,j+1}^k - \psi_{i,j-1}^k) \right], \quad B_j = 0.5\tau \left[\frac{\nu}{h^2} + \frac{1}{4h} (\psi_{i,j+1}^k - \psi_{i,j-1}^k) \right],$$

$$C_j = 1 + \frac{\tau\nu}{h^2}, \quad F_{i,j}^{k+1/2} = \omega_{i,j}^{k+1/2} + \frac{0.5\tau\nu}{h^2} (\omega_{i+1,j}^{k+1/2} - 2\omega_{i,j}^{k+1/2} + \omega_{i-1,j}^{k+1/2}) +$$

$$+ \frac{0.5\tau}{4h} (\omega_{i+1,j}^{k+1/2} - \omega_{i-1,j}^{k+1/2}) (\psi_{i,j+1}^k - \psi_{i,j-1}^k) + Q(t_{k+1}, x_i, y_j).$$

(17) ayirmali tenglamani progonka usuli bilan ω_{ij}^{k+1} larni topish uchun $O(N^2)$ arifmetik amallar talab qilinadi. Taqqoslash uchun shuni ta'kidlaymizki, uyurma tenglamasining ikki o'lchovli oshkormas sxemasini Gauss usuli yordamida yechish uchun $O(N^6)$ arifmetik amallarni talab qilanadi.

(13), (16), (17) tenglamalar quyidagi chegaraviy shartlari bilan to'ldiriladi

$$\psi_{i,0}^{k+1} = 0, \quad \psi_{i,N}^{k+1} = 0, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, N \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, M-1. \quad (18)$$

$$\psi_{0,j}^{k+1} = 0, \quad \psi_{N,j}^{k+1} = 0, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, N \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, M-1.. \quad (19)$$

va chegaraviy tugunlarda uyurma qiymatlarini aniqlash uchun ushbu Vuds shartlari [6] qo'llaniladi:

$$\omega_{i,0}^{k+1} + \frac{\omega_{i,1}^{k+1}}{2} = \frac{3(\psi_{i,0}^k - \psi_{i,1}^k)}{h^2}, \quad \omega_{i,N}^{k+1} + \frac{\omega_{i,N-1}^{k+1}}{2} = \frac{3(\psi_{i,N}^k - \psi_{i,N-1}^k)}{h^2}, \quad (20)$$

$$\omega_{0,j}^{k+1} + \frac{\omega_{1,j}^{k+1}}{2} = \frac{3(\psi_{0,j}^k - \psi_{1,j}^k)}{h^2}, \quad \omega_{N,j}^{k+1} + \frac{\omega_{N-1,j}^{k+1}}{2} = \frac{3(\psi_{N,j}^k - \psi_{N-1,j}^k)}{h^2}. \quad (21)$$

(16),(20) va (17),(21) ayirmali tenglamalar sistemalari progonka usuli bilan yechiladi.

(16),(20) chegaraviy masalalar progonka usuli bilan yechish algoritmini keltiramiz:

$$\omega_{i,j}^{k+1/2} = \bar{\alpha}_{i+1}\omega_{i+1,j}^{k+1/2} + \bar{\beta}_{i+1}, \quad i = N-1, N-2, \dots, 1, 0, \quad (0 < j < N), \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, M-1 \quad (22)$$

$$\bar{\alpha}_{i+1} = \frac{\bar{B}_i}{\bar{C}_i - \bar{A}_i\bar{\alpha}_i}, \quad \bar{\beta}_{i+1} = \frac{\bar{A}_i\bar{\beta}_i + \bar{F}_{ij}^k}{\bar{C}_i - \bar{A}_i\bar{\alpha}_i}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N-1, \quad (0 < j < N), \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, M-1. \quad (23)$$

$$\omega_{0,j}^{k+1/2} = \bar{\alpha}_1\omega_{1,j}^{k+1/2} + \bar{\beta}_1, \quad \omega_{0,j}^{k+1/2} = -\frac{1}{2}\omega_{1,j}^{k+1/2} + \frac{3(\psi_{0j}^k - \psi_{1j}^k)}{h^2},$$

$$\bar{\alpha}_1 = -0,5, \quad \bar{\beta}_1 = \frac{3(\psi_{0j}^k - \psi_{1j}^k)}{h^2}, \quad (0 < j < N), \quad (24)$$

$$\omega_{N,j}^{k+1/2} + \frac{\omega_{N-1,j}^{k+1/2}}{2} = \frac{3(\psi_{N,j}^k - \psi_{N-1,j}^k)}{h^2}, \quad (25)$$

$$\omega_{N-1,j}^{k+1/2} = \bar{\alpha}_N\omega_{N,j}^{k+1/2} + \bar{\beta}_N, \quad (26)$$

(26) ni (25) ga qo'yib to'ring $i = N$ chegaraviy tugunidagi qiymatni aniqlash uchun ushbu ifodaga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\omega_{N,j}^{k+1/2} = \left[\frac{3(\psi_{N,j}^k - \psi_{N-1,j}^k)}{h^2} - 0,5\bar{\beta}_N \right] / (1 + 0,5\bar{\alpha}_N), \quad (27)$$

endi esa (17), (21) chegaraviy masalani progonka usuli bilan yechish algoritmini keltiramiz:

$$\omega_{i,j}^{k+1} = \alpha_{j+1}\omega_{i,j+1}^{k+1} + \beta_{j+1}, \quad j = N-1, N-2, \dots, 1, 0, \quad (0 < i < N), \quad (28)$$

$$\alpha_{j+1} = \frac{B_j}{C_j - A_j\alpha_j}, \quad \beta_{j+1} = \frac{A_j\beta_j + F_{i,j}^{k+1/2}}{C_j - A_j\alpha_j}, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, N-1, \quad (0 < i < N), \quad (29)$$

$$\omega_{i,0}^{k+1} = \alpha_1\omega_{i,1}^{k+1} + \beta_1, \quad \omega_{i,0}^{k+1} = -0,5\omega_{i,0}^{k+1} + 3(\psi_{i,0}^k - \psi_{i,1}^k)/h^2,$$

$$\alpha_1 = -0,5, \quad \beta_1 = 3(\psi_{i,0}^k - \psi_{i,1}^k)/h^2, \quad (0 < i < N), \quad (30)$$

$$\omega_{i,N}^{k+1} + 0,5\omega_{i,N-1}^{k+1} = 3\left(\psi_{i,N}^k - \psi_{i,N-1}^k\right)/h^2, \quad (31)$$

$$\omega_{i,N-1}^{k+1} = \alpha_N \omega_{i,N}^{k+1} + \beta_N, \quad (32)$$

shundan so'ng, yuqoridagiga o'xshash $j = N$ da $\omega_{i,N}^{k+1}$ quyidagi ko'rinishda aniqlanadi:

$$\omega_{i,N}^{k+1} = \left[\frac{3\left(\psi_{i,N}^k - \psi_{i,N-1}^k\right)}{h^2} - 0,5\beta_N \right] / (1 + 0,5\alpha_N). \quad (33)$$

3. Sonli natijalari va xulosalar. Yuqoridagi usullar asosida Navye-Stoks tenglamasini yechish uchun sonli hisoblar natijalarini keltiramiz .

(7)-(10) masalani sonli yechish uchun Pismen-Rekford va yuqori relaksatsiyali iteratsiya usullari qo'llandi. To'rlar quyidagicha tanlandi: $h_x = h_y = 0.05$, $\nu = 1$, $\tau = 0.001$. Sinov funktsiyasi usuli yordamida hisoblash tajribasini o'tkazamiz. Agar differensial masala $\psi(t, x, y) = t \cdot \sin^2 \pi x \cdot \sin^2 2\pi y$ aniq yechimga ega bo'lsa, u holda $\omega(t, x, y)$ va $Q(t, x, y)$ uchun ifodani aniqlashimiz mumkin[7].

Joriy (2) tenglamadan biz funktsiya uchun formulalarni $\omega(x, y)$ olamiz :

$$\omega(t, x, y) = -\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial y^2}. \quad (34)$$

Keling, hosilalarni topaylik

$$\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} = 2\pi^2 t \cos 2\pi x \sin^2 2\pi y, \quad \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial y^2} = 8\pi^2 t \cos 4\pi y \sin^2 2\pi x$$

Topilgan hosilalarni berib , **Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.** funktsiya uchun quyidagi formulalarni $\omega(t, x, y)$ olamiz :

$\omega(t, x, y) = -2\pi^2 t(-10 \cdot \sin^2 \pi x \cdot \sin^2 2\pi y + 4 \cdot \sin^2 \pi x + \sin^2 2\pi y)$
uyurma tenglamasidan (1) biz uchun $Q(t, x, y)$

$$Q(t, x, y) = \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} \cdot \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} - \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial y^2} \right) \quad (35)$$

(34) ni (35) ga qo'yib $Q(t, x, y)$ uchun quyidagi ifodaga ega bo'lamiz:

$$Q(t, x, y) = -\left(\frac{\partial^3 \psi}{\partial x^2 \partial t} + \frac{\partial^3 \psi}{\partial y^2 \partial t} \right) - \left(\frac{\partial^3 \psi}{\partial x^3} + \frac{\partial^3 \psi}{\partial x \partial y^2} \right) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} + \left(\frac{\partial^3 \psi}{\partial x^2 \partial y} + \frac{\partial^3 \psi}{\partial y^3} \right) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial^4 \psi}{\partial x^4} + 2 \frac{\partial^4 \psi}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^4 \psi}{\partial y^4} \right), \quad (36)$$

$\psi(t, x, y)$ funktsiyasi xususiy hosilalarini (36) ga qo'yib $Q(t, x, y)$ uchun quyidagi ifodaga ega bo'lamiz:

$$Q(t, x, y) = 2\pi^2 \cdot (-10\sigma_1\sigma_2^2 + 4\sigma_1 + \sigma_2^2) +$$

$$+ 8\pi^4 t \cdot (44\sigma_1\sigma_2^2 - 22\sigma_1 - 76\sigma_2^2 + 4) +$$

$$+ 16\pi^4 t \cdot \cos \pi x \cdot \sigma_3 \cdot \sin \pi x \cdot \sigma_2^3 / (10 \cdot \cos^2 \pi x - 9) -$$

$$- 32\pi^4 t^2 \cdot \cos \pi x \cdot \sigma_3 \sin^3 \pi x \cdot \sigma_2 \cdot (5\sigma_2^2 - 3),$$

bu yerda $\sigma_1 = \sin^2 \pi x$, $\sigma_2 = \sin 2\pi y$ $\sigma_3 = \cos 2\pi y$.

1-rasm. $\psi(T, x, y)$ o qim funktsiyalari analitik yechimi

a

b

a

t=1.0 dagi yuqori relaksatsiya usuli bilan olingan $\psi(t,x,y)$ oqim funksiyasi sonli yechimi

b

t=1.0 dagi yuqori relaksatsiya usuli bilan olingan $\psi(t,x,y)$ oqim funksiyasi sonli yechimi

2-rasm. $\psi(T, x, y)$ o qim funktsiyalari sonli yechimi

a

b

3-rasm. $\omega(T, x, y)$ uyurma funktsiyalari analitik yechimi

a

$t=1.0$ da Pismen-Rekford sxemasi bo'yicha $\omega(t,x,y)$ olingan sonli yechim

b

$t=1.0$ da Pismen-Rekford sxemasi bo'yicha $\omega(t,x,y)$ olingan sonli yechim

4-rasm. $\omega(T, x, y)$ uyurma funktsiyalari sonli yechimi

Mos ravishda 1-va 3-asmlarda $t=1$ da $\psi(t, x, y)$ oqim va $\omega(t, x, y)$ uyurmalarining analitik yechimi sirt va sath chizziqlari ko‘rinishida tasvirlangan.

2-va 4-rasmlarda esa $t=1$ da $\psi(t, x, y)$ oqim tenglamasining va $\omega(t, x, y)$ uyurma tenglamasining sonli yechimlari tasvirlangan.

1- va 4- rasmlardagi natijalardan ko‘rinadiki, aniq(analitik) va sonli yechimlar deyerli ustma-ust tushmoqda. Bundan “uyurma - oqim” ko‘rinishidagi Navye-Stoks tenglamalar sistemasini sonli yechish uchun Pismen – Rekford usuli va yuqori relaksatsiya iteratsiya usullarini birgalikda qo‘llash yaxshi natija berar ekan.

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